

Effect of ply thickness and temperature on transverse cracking process in composite laminates

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Context and objectives of work thesis

Industrial context

- ❖ Decrease the mass of launch vehicle → Cryogenic tanks in composite without liner

Thesis objectives

- Characterization of crack networks under mechanical and thermal loading (Temperature < 143K)
- Enrich and validate the damage meso-model for prediction of leak path

Cryogenic tank of type III-IV

Crack networks ↔ Leak path

« The industrial objective is sizing of linerless cryogenic tank in composite material »

Experimental characterization

Damage observations of cross-ply laminates under loading

- Carbon fiber / Epoxy matrix
- Different fiber mass (75g/m² and 150 g/m²)
- [0 / 90_n / 0 / 90_k / 0 / 90_n / 0]

- Rectangular specimen (AFP Process)
- Numerous step loading
- Three testing temperature (293K to 143K)
- Quantification of N transverse cracks

Numerical model

Virtual testing of transverse cracking process

- Transverse crack ↔ Cohesive Zone Model
- Damage initiation : Strain quadratic criterion $\left(\frac{\langle\sigma_n\rangle}{\sigma_n^0}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\langle\sigma_s\rangle}{\sigma_s^0}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\langle\sigma_t\rangle}{\sigma_t^0}\right)^2 = 1$
- Damage evolution : Cracking energetic criterion $G^c = G_n^c + (G_s^c - G_n^c) \left(\frac{G_s}{G_n + G_s}\right)^\eta$ (Benzeggagh-Kenane)
- Variability effects : Weibull distribution $P(\sigma) = 1 - \exp\left(-\left(\frac{\sigma - \sigma_{th}}{\sigma_0}\right)^k\right)$

Experimental analysis and confrontation with the numerical model

Conclusions and prospects

- ✓ Thickness ply effect → Thin plies push up the cracking threshold → The cracking rate is lower for thin plies
- ✓ Temperature effect → Lower damage threshold for low temperature → Quicker damage kinetic for low temperature → Higher cracking rate for low temperatures
- ✓ Numerical model → Good correlation with experimental data → Identification of damage scenario
- Future studies → Fitting with experimental data at low temperature → 3D modelling for many stacking sequences

Evolution of reduce crack rate according to longitudinal stress laminate

